

Validation of ESA EO Aerosol Height products with EARLINET Lidar observations

Final report

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Executive summary

The purpose of our study is to investigate the ability of the TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) on board on the Sentinel-5P, to deliver accurate geometrical features of lofted aerosol layers in a continental scale. Comparisons with ground-based correlative measurements constitute a key component in the validation of passive satellite products related to aerosol properties. For this purpose, we use ground-based lidar data from lidar stations belonging to the European Aerosol Research Lidar, EARLINET, network. In the frame of this work, we have developed and applied an optimal methodology for validation purposes using EARLINET optical profiles and TROPOMI aerosol products, aiming at the investigation of Aerosol Layer Height product. The approach followed is based on the previous expertise and methodology that have been firstly developed and applied in EARLINET for the GOME-2/MetOp validation activities. We are looking for collocated cases between EARLINET and TROPOMI/S5P overpasses for the time period 2018 – 2021, over the Mediterranean Basin which is selected as the domain of interest. We focus on selecting lidar stations located near the sea, because the ALH retrieval becomes unreliable over the land. Overall, for 7 selected EARLINET stations across the Mediterranean, 25 coincident aerosol cases were found, checked and flagged for the comparison against satellite retrievals. The presented validation methodology uses the lidar backscatter profiles and collocated TROPOMI ALH pixels using ± 3 h and a radius of 150km as spatiotemporal collocation thresholds. We find high correlation, of $R=0.96$, between satellite and ground-based data, but also that TROPOMI ALH values underestimate by -1.2 ± 0.86 km on average the ground-based lidar observations for the selected cases with a remarkable aerosol load.

The GOME-2 Absorbing Aerosol Height validation against EARLINET lidar profiles can be viewed in the relevant publication:

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1 Introduction

In the following, we report on the activities performed within the European Space Agency Quality Assurance for Earth Observation, QA4EO, project, Work Package 2191, titled *Validation of ESA EO Aerosol Height products with EARLINET Lidar observations*. For the purposes of this work, European Aerosol Research Lidar Network ([EARLINET](#)) data records for the period from 2018 to 2021 were acquired and post-processed with the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics, LAP/Auth, dedicated software in order to identify lofted aerosol layers and exclude all cases of cloud presence contamination. The [SSP/TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height](#) profiles were downloaded and post-processed so as to study the possible effects of other geophysical parameters of the satellite L2 algorithm in order to clearly identify aerosol layers. The proposed validation strategy follows the methodology presented in Michailidis et al. (2021a) for the GOME-2 AAH validation against EARLINET and was modified to compare TROPOMI ALH. The dedicated LAP/Auth Aerosol Validation Chain was then applied to the entire timeline.

The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height product has a number of important applications, notably for aviation safety purposes, but also for a range of scientific research themes. A large-scale global validation of the Aerosol Layer Height product is essential to understand the quality and performance of the sensor and algorithm. Since the altitude of aerosols is difficult to determine from space using passive sensors, validation processes are best carried out with active satellite aerosol remote sensing observations (e.g. CALIPSO) or ground-based lidars (e.g. EARLINET network). Due to the variable distribution of aerosols in space and time, an accurate validation against independent ground-based measurements is needed in order to evaluate the quality of the TROPOMI retrievals. In the first year (2018–2019) assessment of TROPOMI operational ALH retrievals against the CALIOP-based ALH data, Nanda et al. (2020) indicated that operational algorithm retrieves lower ALH compared to CALIOP, by ~ 2 km over land and ~ 0.5 km over ocean. Over ocean and dark land, the main difference is attributed to the difference in the sensor sensitivity to aerosol layers, centroid for TROPOMI, top of the plume for CALIOP. A similar comparison for the 2018 North American fires indicates that this bias also strongly depends on the thickness of the smoke plume, which controls the relative contribution of the satellite signal from the surface (Griffin et al., 2020). For instance, a -2.1 km bias of ALH is found for thin plumes, but that is reduced to only -0.7 km on average for plumes thicker than 1.5 km. These results were confirmed by the Multi-angle Imaging SpectroRadiometer (MISR) stereoscopic plume height retrievals as well (Griffin et al., 2020). In this work, we focus on the validation against ground-based lidars around the Mediterranean Sea during Saharan dust events and long range transport of smoke aerosols.

This report is structured as follows: Section 2 contains the description of the different satellite and ground-based data sets, while subsection 2.3 contains the detailed description of the validation strategy, the quality control and product limitations. In Section 3 we provide the main validation results and statistics as well as a case study in detail, so as to demonstrate the full potential of presented method. Section 4 provides a discussion of the results and finally, conclusions and prospects are summarized in Section 5.

2 Data and Methodology

A short description of instruments and data used in this study is presented in next sub-sections, including a short explanation on the methodology that we followed for validation purposes.

2.1 European Aerosol Research Lidar Network | EARLINET

Lidar is the most prominent tool for aerosol profiling and has largely contributed to our knowledge of the vertical distribution of the aerosol optical properties (e.g., Balis et al., 2004, Papayannis et al., 2008; Amiridis et al. 2009; Mona et al., 2012; Granados-Muñoz et al., 2016). The European Aerosol Research Lidar Network (Pappalardo et al. 2014) established in 2000, provides an excellent opportunity to offer a large collection of quality-assured ground-based data of the vertical distribution of the aerosol optical properties over Europe. The geographic and temporal coverage of EARLINET stations as well as the reported quality assured measurements provides an excellent framework for the intercomparison of TROPOMI/S5P products under different atmospheric conditions and aerosol concentrations. Ground-based lidar measurements provide backscatter profiles and in some cases extinction profiles. These profiles can unambiguously indicate the presence of aerosol and cloud layers. If the optical thickness of the aerosols and clouds takes high values, then multiple aerosol and cloud layers can be detected. Information on aerosol properties and aerosol type is sometimes also available, depending on the specific lidar technique (Klett et al. 1981, 1985; Ansmann et al., 1992). The majority of the EARLINET stations are equipped with multi-wavelength Raman channels and many of them operate depolarization channels that measure the depolarization of the emitted linearly polarized radiation. In order to ensure qualitative and consistent data processing within the EARLINET network, algorithm intercomparison campaigns have been organized (Wandinger et al. 2016; Amodeo et al., 2020). EARLINET data have been used extensively for satellite aerosol products validation in the last years, such as for the Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations (CALIPSO) (Winker et al., 2009), which is the first satellite focused on monitoring vertically resolved aerosol and cloud optical and geometrical products (Omar et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2017). The first validation of absorbing aerosol height product from GOME-2 on board the MetOp satellite platforms was also achieved by using the quality-assured EARLINET products (Michailidis et al., 2021a). Since the lidar networks are designed with long-term observation in mind, the EARLINET is also a suitable source for the long-term validation for the TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height data product. The EARLINET network lidar measurements can be used on a case study basis to evaluate specific aerosol episodes or they may be compiled into a larger validation set comprising many validation sites over a longer period of time to allow for a statistical analysis. A more extensive analysis is currently in preparation for publication (Michailidis et al., 2021b).

Mediterranean Sea basin

The Mediterranean Sea consists of a region surrounded by the Sahara Desert on the south and the highly populated and industrialized Europe on the north. This region has been identified as cross roads of air masses containing different types of aerosols (see for e.g. Lelieveld et al., 2002). The atmospheric aerosol composition over the Mediterranean region is geographically dependent and the aerosol concentration is mainly characterized by continental, both of natural (biogenic, mineral, biomass burning) and of anthropogenic (urban and industrial fine particles) origin aerosols, superimposed by maritime and coarse African dust particles. The location of the EARLINET stations is highly interesting due to their proximity to the Sahara Desert and South Europe, so frequent events of mineral dust and smoke particles could be detected

by both lidars and TROPOMI. The sites are located across the Mediterranean basin and were chosen to represent different latitudes, longitudes and topography, see **Table 1** and **Figure 1** for their geographical spread.

Figure 1. Location of EARLINET lidar stations used in this study. Red circles denote multi-wavelength Raman lidars and green denotes the PollyXT lidar systems indicated in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Locations of EARLINET lidar stations order by site, with their geographical coordinates and number of TROPOMI collocations considered in the validation process.

Station	Code	Country	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Elevation (m.a.s.l)	Cases
Antikythera	AKY	Greece	23.31	35.86	193	8
Athens	ATZ	Greece	23.78	37.96	212	1
Évora	EVO	Portugal	7.91	38.56	293	3
Granada	GRA	Spain	-3.60	37.16	680	4
Lecce	SAL	Italy	18.10	40.33	30	2
Limassol	LIM	Cyprus	33.04	34.67	10	6
Potenza	POT	Italy	15.72	40.60	760	1

Lidar layer height retrievals

A common product of all lidar observations is the profiling capability, that is, the aerosol layering. In order to characterize the detected aerosol layers, in terms of their geometrical properties, parameters such as the layer base (Z_{BASE}), layer top (Z_{TOP}), layer thickness (L_{TH}) and center of mass (Z_{COM}), can be calculated from the lidar signals. In this study, we make use of the weighted-backscatter height (ALH_{bsc}), calculated as the center of mass on backscatter profile, based on the methodology described in Mona et al. (2006). This height parameter is an important indicator for vertical profiles that gives in a single number an indication of the altitude of the aerosol distribution. In cases where a single aerosol layer is present in the atmosphere, the ALH_{bsc} gives an indication of its mean altitude; in case of multiple layers however, the ALH_{bsc} could be located in areas without any considerable aerosol load. This parameter is considered ideal for comparisons with aerosol layer height retrievals from passive remote sensing (e.g. TROPOMI/S5P, GOME-2/MetOp and upcoming Sentinel-4 & 5 missions; Ingmann et al. 2012).

Furthermore, in our study we apply the WCT (Wavelet Covariance Transform) approach following the work proposed within Michailidis et al. (2021a) for automatic layer detection (see Appendix A for details on a case study). Once the top and base of the aerosol layer are identified, the center of mass of each aerosol layer can be also estimated from lidar profiles. Information about the aerosol layer center of mass is useful because the characteristics of the detected layer can be distinguished at this altitude. Under the detection of a homogenous aerosol layer, the center of mass can be estimated as the mean altitude of the identified aerosol layer weighted by the altitude-dependent aerosol backscatter coefficient. In some cases, the aerosol vertical structure is very complicated because aerosol layers are present at different heights. For these cases a total layer resulting from the multi-layered structure is considered for the calculation of mean optical parameters and integrated values. The weighted-backscatter altitude is estimated by the equation:

$$ALH_{b_{sc}} = \frac{\int_{z_i=1}^{z=n} z_i \cdot \beta_{aer,i}(z) dz}{\int_{z_i=1}^{z=n} \beta_{aer,i}(z) dz} \quad (1)$$

where $\beta_{aer,i}$ represents the aerosol backscatter coefficient ($Mm^{-1} \cdot sr^{-1}$) primarily at 1064 nm channel at level i and Z_i is the altitude (km) of level i for the aerosol profile signal. Based on the above equation, the layer height is calculated from backscatter profiles, symbolized as $ALH_{b_{sc}}$ (or $ALH_{EARLINET}$). The $ALH_{b_{sc}}$ represents an effective ALH weighted by the aerosol backscatter signal at each level and is consistent with ALH as defined in the TROPOMI algorithm. In our work analysis, we applied **Eq. 1**, to all lidar backscatter profiles collocated to TROPOMI measurements.

2.2 TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument | TROPOMI

The TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI; Veefkind et al., 2012) is a space-borne, nadir-viewing, imaging spectrometer covering wavelength bands between the ultraviolet and the shortwave infrared. Sentinel-5P is a near-polar sun-synchronous orbit satellite flying at an altitude of 817 km, with a 2600 km wide swath, providing near-daily global coverage and overpass local time at ascending node of 13:30 (repeat cycle of 17 days). TROPOMI uses passive remote sensing techniques to attain its objective by measuring, at the Top Of Atmosphere (TOA), the solar radiation reflected by and radiated from the earth. The spatial resolution at nadir, originally of $3.5 \times 7 \text{ km}^2$ (across-track \times along-track) has been refined to $3.5 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$ on 6 August 2019.

The **TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height product** focuses on the retrieval of vertically localized aerosol layers in the free troposphere, such as desert dust, biomass burning aerosol, or volcanic ash plumes. The height of such layers is retrieved for cloud-free conditions. Retrieval of aerosol height is based on absorption in the O₂A band in the near-infrared wavelength range (759-770 nm) and assumes a single aerosol layer with 50 hPa thickness. The O₂-A band can provide altitude information on scattering layers (clouds or aerosol) from the troposphere up to the stratosphere. The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height (AER_LH) algorithm was developed by the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI; Sanders et al., 2015) and is a part of TROPOMI's operational algorithm suite. Detailed description of the original ALH algorithm, including aerosol optical models used and the aerosol type detection method, can be also found in Nanda et al. 2019.

For this study, we use TROPOMI L2 (OFFL and RPRO) ALH data during the period 2018-2021, retrieved using the scientific algorithm developed by KNMI, optimized to retrieve Aerosol Layer Height. Additionally, we use TROPOMI operational UVAI data to examine the consistency of these two observational products over

selected domain. In brief, for this product, several quality control filters are applied in the TROPOMI L2 dataset, following the filtering proposed for ALH product (Nanda et al. 2020; Table 1). Detailed description of the changes can be found in appropriate versions of the Product User Manual (PUM; Apituley, et al., 2021) and Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD; de Graaf, et al., 2021) associated with the ALH product.

The **TROPOMI UV aerosol index (AI)** is an air quality product derived from the TOA reflectance spectra and is widely used as an indicator for the presence of absorbing aerosols in the atmosphere. The UVAI is based on spectral contrast in the ultraviolet (UV) spectral range for a given wavelength pair, where the difference between the observed reflectance and the modelled clear-sky reflectance results in a residual value. It should be noted that for S5P TROPOMI the UVAI is an operational TROPOMI product, calculated for two wavelength pairs, 388/354 nm and 340/380nm, the first one allowing a direct comparison to the UVAI from OMI. Both wavelength pairs are included in the Level-2 UVAI product. When this residual is positive it indicates the presence of UV-absorbing aerosols, like dust, smoke, or volcanic ash. Clouds yield near-zero residual values and negative residual values can be indicative of the presence of non-absorbing aerosols, as shown by sensitivity studies of the UVAI (e.g. de Graaf et al., 2005; Kooreman et al. 2020). The UVAI can also be calculated in the presence of clouds, so that daily global coverage is possible. This is ideal for tracking the evolution of extreme aerosol layers from dust outbreaks, biomass burning, volcanic eruptions. For more details about the TROPOMI UVAI retrieval algorithm, see Stein-Zweers et al. (2018).

The TROPOMI pixel selection scheme and flags applied is enumerated here, following the recommendation by the Product User Manual (PUM) and Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD):

- i. Pixels with an associated quality assurance value of less than 0.5 were excluded.
- ii. Pixels with an associated negative AI are excluded, hence only desert dust, biomass burning aerosol and volcanic ash aerosols – i.e. absorbing aerosols – remain in the dataset.
- iii. Pixels with a raised sunglint flag are excluded.
- iv. Pixels over land are excluded, due to known surface albedo issues (Sanders et al. 2015).
- v. Pixels with an associated cloud percentage are excluded. Clouds strongly bias the TROPOMI ALH towards the cloud altitude. Additional cloud screening, which is available in the product in the form of flags, is essential for retrieving proper aerosol layer heights.

All the above quality control procedures and filtering criteria applied in the final dataset, are summarized in Nanda et al. (2020; Table 1).

2.3 Validation methodology and collocation criteria

Taking into account the recommendations of the previous comparison studies (Griffin et al., 2020 ; Nanda et al., 2020), the selection of data and the comparison between TROPOMI and the EARLINET datasets estimates of aerosol heights proceed through the following steps, for each date:

1. Make a list of TROPOMI overpass swaths that are within the region of interest (EARLINET stations).
2. Identify the closest TROPOMI pixels (within a radii of 150km) around EARLINET stations in time and space. A maximum time difference of ± 3 h is allowed between collocation pairs.
3. For each ground-based measurement, the spatially averaged TROPOMI pixels in a radii of 150km, were selected for the comparison study.

4. As input to the validation processing, we use the lidar backscatter coefficient profiles at 1064 nm (or 532 nm), analyzed by the Single Calculus Chain (SCC) algorithm (D'Amico et al., 2015, 2016) for quality-assured measurements and TROPOMI Level-2 OFFL and RPRO ALH product.
5. In order to make an accurate validation analysis we apply quality screening flags, to eliminate samples and layers that were detected or classified with very low confidence or that contained untrustworthy height retrievals. Furthermore, EARLINET observations have been carefully checked, and atmospheric conditions have been studied to ensure that cloud-scenes are excluded from the profiles.
6. For the layer height retrieval from the EARLINET products, we used the methodology proposed by Mona et al. (2006) to calculate the weighted backscatter height using the Level-2 backscatter profiles 1064 nm (or 532nm). Furthermore, we apply the WCT method in order to identify the aerosol layer boundaries from the detected layers.
7. Finally, we provide a detailed analysis between the two dataset and the first results including statistic metrics are discussed.

The validation of products with a typical resolution of several kilometres against point-like ground-based measurements involves uncertainties. A key question is how well the ground-based observation represents a larger area around the measurement site and to a large extent depends on the characteristics of the station location (urban, suburban, etc.). In this study, to obtain a significant number of collocated TROPOMI – EARLINET cases, data from 7 EARLINET stations were used for the TROPOMI ALH product validation (**Table 1**). For the comparison of TROPOMI ALH against aerosol height from EARLINET lidars, the spatial coincidence criteria are set to a 150 km search radius between the satellite pixel centre and the geolocation of the ground-based station. The lidar measurements closest to the TROPOMI overpass time within a 3 h temporal interval were selected for every available day of measurement to ensure a sufficiently high number of collocations. It should also be noted that the temporal criterion is necessary since most of the EARLINET lidar observations occur at noon or night. To reduce mismatch errors due to the significant difference in horizontal sensitivity between S5P and lidar measurements, individual TROPOMI ALH data, are averaged over a selected radius around the study stations. The validation strategy we followed as well as the development stages for the validation tool well-described in this final report, are also mentioned in the quarterly reports in the framework of the QA4EO project.

The methodology is demonstrated using a selected number of collocated cases of TROPOMI overpasses over selected EARLINET lidar stations located across the Mediterranean for the period June 2018 to June 2021. The approach followed is mostly based on the previous expertise and methodology that have been firstly developed and applied in EARLINET for the GOME2 cal/val activities (Michailidis et al., 2021a). A flowchart illustrating the main steps followed to validate satellite-derived aerosol height product is presented in Appendix (Fig. A5). At present, 7 EARLINET stations operating the 1064 nm (or 532 nm) channel contribute to this study. The permanent stations are located at: Antikythera (Greece), Athens (Greece), Évora (Portugal), Granada (Spain), Lecce (Italy), Limassol (Cyprus) and Potenza (Italy). The total available dataset is quite small, resulted in a total of 25 cases for the period between June 2018 – June 2021 suitable for the comparison study and representativeness of the TROPOMI ALH product. The list of all co-locations is presented in **Table A 1**, which includes the names of the EARLINET stations, the TROPOMI ALH value from averaged pixels and the calculated EARLINET ALH_{bsc}.

3 Validation Results

In the following section, we first provide an example case study as demonstration for the validation analysis performed (Section 3.1), followed by the analysis of the entire collocative cases found for the period studied (Section 3.2). The validation chain flowchart is shown in **Figure A 5**.

3.1 Analysis of selected EARLINET & TROPOMI dust cases

Below, we provide an example showing the EARLINET/TROPOMI validation analysis for a major mineral desert dust scene over the Mediterranean basin. The selected case refers to a special extreme dust event over central-east Mediterranean on the 9th and 10th of January 2021. This event was observed by the PANhellenic Geophysical observatory of Antikythera (PANGEA) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) in the remote island of Antikythera (Greece) on the first day and the Limassol EARLINET station in Cyprus on the second day. The presented cases are representative for cloud-free and relative homogeneous atmospheric scenes in terms of aerosol load, demonstrating the general performance of TROPOMI/S5P under such conditions.

Saharan dust event on the 9th and 10th of January 2021

The Mediterranean was affected by a strong dust episode originating from North Africa during the 9th and 10th of January 2021. Lofted layers of dust were observed during these days by PollyXT systems operating at PANGEA–Antikythera and Limassol stations. The multi-wavelength observations of PollyXT contain unique fingerprints of the observed aerosol types from different source regions (Engelmann et al. 2016; Ansmann et al. 2018). The evolution of dust advection from the Sahara towards Greece and Cyprus is shown in **Figure 2**, as described by the DREAM-bsc dust model for the 9-10 January 2021. This figure shows that large quantities of aerosol dust are present along the northern boundaries of the African continent and also over the Mediterranean Sea, particularly over -South Italy and Greece. These high aerosol dust loadings move eastward the following day (10 January), mainly over Cyprus giving local values of AOT between 0.4–0.7, according to AERONET data (“CUT-TEPAK” AERONET station, not shown here). In the past, several studies of the vertical variability of dust aerosol geometrical, optical and microphysical properties have been performed in the European continent by the synergy of ground-based lidars, in-situ instruments, satellite observations and model simulations, mainly in the frame of the EARLINET network (Balis et al. 2004; Kokkalis et al. 2020).

Figure 2. Dust load over Eastern Mediterranean Europe on (left) 9 January 2021 and (right) 10 January 2021 when Saharan dust aerosol was present in the free-troposphere over Antikythera (Greece) and Limassol (Cyprus), respectively, according the DREAM-bsc dust forecast.

9 January 2021, Antikythera (Greece)

PANGEA observatory of NOA in the remote island of Antikythera, is located across the travel path of different air masses, providing continuous monitoring of essential climate variables in the Eastern Mediterranean (Kampouri et al., 2021). The Aerosol Remote Sensing facility of ACTRIS (Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure; <https://www.actris.eu>) is collecting continuous observations of aerosols and clouds since 2018. A PollyXT-NOA lidar (Englemann et al., 2016; Baars et al., 2017) is installed since August 2018. This type of lidar, is a multi-wavelength Raman-polarization system with 24/7 operational capabilities, providing vertical distributions of the particle backscatter coefficient (β_{aer}) at 355, 532 and 1064 nm, the extinction coefficient (α_{aer}) at 355 and 532 nm and the particle depolarization ratio (δ_p) at 355 and 532 nm. The measurement dataset presented herein is used in order to validate the TROPOMI ALH retrievals for a 150km radius distance around the station.

To illustrate the evaluation methodology for the TROPOMI Level- 2 ALH, a pair of collocated and concurrent TROPOMI and EARLINET lidar observations is shown in **Figure 3**. The example refers to a Sentinel-5P overpass of the Antikythera, Greece, on 9 January 2021. During that period, the PollyXT NOA system was operating in a 24/7 mode in PANGEA observatory. The dust plume can be clearly seen in **Figure 3** (left) over Greece from the VIIRS/Suomi-NPP true color image for this day (VIIRS images available at: <https://wvs.earthdata.nasa.gov/>; last access: 5 Oct 2021). **Figure 3** also displays the TROPOMI ALH (middle) and UVAI (right) spatial distribution from TROPOMI observations on this day during the Sentinel-5P overpass over eastern Mediterranean. The TROPOMI ALH retrieved pixels are situated in between the surface and 2.5 km and UVAI values ranging between 0.2-1. These maps show that a significant dust plume covered both the eastern Mediterranean, also dispersing over part of Southern Italy, including the island of Antikythera. Comparing the UVAI map to the VIIRS image and the TROPOMI ALH shows that the UVAI pixels are located at the main part of the detected plume. This figure also shows the impact of cloud contamination in our dataset.

Figure 3. (Left) VIIRS RGB image on 9 January 2021 when the SNPP satellite passed over Antikythera island (35.86° N, 23.31° E, alt: 193m), (middle) TROPOMI ALH product and (right) TROPOMI UVAI at 354/388nm pair. The red star denotes the Antikythera EARLINET station.

Figure 4 (left) presents the total attenuated backscatter signal time-series for the PollyXT at 1064nm, over Antikythera during 06:00-12:00 UTC on 9 January 2021. The aerosol load was mainly between 500 and 4000 m and the sky above the site was cloud-free during the TROPOMI overpass. In order to verify the origin of the detected aerosol layers, observed by the ground-based lidar and TROPOMI/S5P satellite, we calculated back-trajectories by using the HYSPLIT model (Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory; available online: last access: 4 Oct 2021) (Stein et al. 2015; Rolph et al. 2017). The temporal evolution of 3-day backward trajectories, for 9 January 2021 for arrival heights: 1000 (red), 2000 (green) and 3500 m (yellow) is illustrated

in **Figure 4 (right)**. As can be seen, the air masses which arrived over Antikythera station seemed to follow a similar pattern. They originated from North-western Africa and, after leaving the African continent, followed an almost straight route path towards Greece.

Figure 4. (Left) Temporal evolution of the total attenuated backscatter signal from the PANGEA PollyXT at 1064nm. (Right) 3-day back-trajectories arriving at Antikythera, Greece on 9 January 2021 at 12:00 (Data from HYSPLIT accessible at www.ready.noaa.gov)

In **Figure 5** the closest in time averaged vertical backscatter profile (11:30–12:00 UTC) is illustrated, measured by the PollyXT lidar system. **Figure 5 (left)** illustrates the WCT applied on the backscatter profile at 1064 nm. A clear single layer with large aerosol load was observed according to the backscatter vertical profiles, and using the WCT automatic method we extracted the layer boundaries. For the predominant thick layer, the retrieved geometric properties are: layer base (2016m), layer top (3271m), layer thickness (1255m) and center of mass (2582m). Accordingly, the TROPOMI ALH spatially averaged values and the EARLINET temporally averaged backscatter coefficient profiles (between 11:30-12:00 UTC) are qualitatively compared in **Figure 5 (right)**. TROPOMI detects this layer height approximately around 1570m and the calculated $ALH_{b_{sc}}$ from lidar profile is 2151m. A fair agreement between the satellite and ground-based lidar systems is shown for this aerosol scene. It is clear that the center of the assumed layer height by the TROPOMI operational algorithm is lower but very close to the actual layer location calculated as $ALH_{b_{sc}}$ height (difference=600 m). The presented case study indicates that under cloud-free conditions where a homogeneous aerosol layer is developed, the mean ALH value retrieved by the TROPOMI is in good agreement with the calculated $ALH_{b_{sc}}$ from lidar profile. This assumption is confirmed with results obtained by other findings in the literature for TROPOMI ALH validation studies by Griffin et al. (2020) and Nanda et al. (2020).

Figure 5. (Left) (a) backscatter coefficient profile at 1064 nm retrieved at the EARLINET station of Antikythera and (b) resulting WCT profile on 9th of January 2021, between 11:30–12:00 UTC. The horizontal dashed red, blue and yellow lines represent the aerosol layer top, base and center of mass. Magenta area indicates the layer thickness. (Right) TROPOMI mean ALH (green dashed line) comparison to the retrieved lidar $ALH_{b_{sc}}$ (red dashed line).

10 January 2021, Limassol (Cyprus)

The island of Cyprus is a unique spot in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea where different and very complex aerosol mixtures occur (Mamouri et al., 2013). The lidar station at Limassol (34.6°N, 33.04°E, alt: 10m) (Mamouri et al., 2021) is member of the EARLINET and PollyNet (Baars et al., 2017; Engelman et al., 2016). A new generation PollyXT lidar system has been started on 27th of October 2020, continuous operation, as the PollyXT-CYP aims to link the Centre to both ACTRIS and PollyNet (<https://polly.tropos.de/>) networks. The system is continuously running and, since the first observations in Limassol, PollyXT-CYP demonstrates the complex aerosol conditions over Cyprus. This multi-wavelength system is equipped with three elastic channels at 355, 532 and 1064 nm; two Raman channels at 387 and 607 nm; two channels for the detection of the cross-polarized backscattered signal at 355 and 532 nm; and one water vapour channel at 407 nm. For the 10th of January 2021, the PollyXT system confirmed the presence of atmospheric dust with a single distinct dust layer was observed between 2000–4000 m a.s.l.

According to **Figure 6** (left), a True color image from VIIRS/Suomi-NPP spectral signal reveal the presence of dust plume over the Cyprus for the January 10, 2021. The red star denotes the location of Limassol PollyXT lidar system. **Figure 6** (middle) shows the geographical distribution of TROPOMI ALH and **Figure 6** (right) the corresponding UVAI values over Cyprus. These maps show the extent of the dust plume from the northern part of Africa, as well as the altitude as derived by the TROPOMI ALH product algorithm. The dust provides an opportunity to compare the AER_LH with ground-based measurements, since the extent of the dust plume is so large that the EARLINET station captured well this event. Below, an inspection of PollyXT lidar quicklook revealed extended higher altitudes of the dust derived by PollyXT lidar than by TROPOMI.

Figure 6. (Left) VIIRS RGB image on 10 January 2021 when the SNPP satellite passed over the Cyprus island (34.6°N, 33.04°E, alt: 10m), (middle) TROPOMI ALH and (right) TROPOMI UVAI at 354/388nm pair. The red star denotes the Limassol EARLINET station.

According to the temporal evolution of the total backscatter lidar signal at 1064 nm, shown in **Figure 7 (left)**, there is an almost uniform layer in the atmospheric column above Limassol station, observed between 2000 – 4000 m asl, during the morning of 10th January, 2021. The PollyXT measurements between 09:30 and 12:30 UTC did not report any cloud features either, including any cirrus cloud and the dust plume remains stable over Limassol from the surface to 4 km during the local morning. In order to verify the Saharan dust transport to the Eastern Mediterranean region, we also performed a 3-day back-trajectory analysis provided by the HYSPLIT model. The relevant 72-h back trajectory analysis for air-masses ending over Limassol (Cyprus) at 12:00 UT on 10 January 2021 is presented in **Figure 7 (right)**. All air-mass trajectories ending over Limassol site

at height levels between 1.5 km and 4 km, originated from the North Africa and Sahara area. These air-masses passed over central Italy and then drifted cyclonically eastward toward Greece to transport over the Cyprus.

Figure 7. (Left) Temporal evolution of the total attenuated backscatter signal from the PollyXT at 1064nm. (Right) 3-day back-trajectories arriving at Limassol, Cyprus on 10 January 2021 at 12:00 (Data from HYSPLIT accessible at www.ready.noaa.gov)

In the case of the β_{aer} vertical profile over Limassol (**Figure 8**) a distinct dust layer is visible between 1 and 4 km a.s.l., which has a max value of the order of $6.5 Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$ around to 2.7 km altitude. The high β_{aer} values, are due to the vicinity of this site to the African desert, thus higher dust loadings are found during Saharan dust events. The β_{aer} vertical profile over Limassol closely follows the shape of that over Antikythera up to 4 km (**Figure 5**), showing no distinct dust layers in the upper part of free troposphere. We also apply the WCT method on backscatter profile (**Figure 8, left**) in order to extract the geometrical features of detected layers from the retrieved backscatter coefficients. The horizontal dashed blue and red lines represent the detected aerosol layer top and base while the yellow line denote the center of mass. More specifically: layer base (2130m), layer top (3684m), layer thickness (1550m) and center of mass (2802m). The comparison of the weighted-backscatter altitude from the mean backscatter coefficient profiles retrieved by PollyXT lidar and the corresponding TROPOMI averaged ALH values are presented in (**Figure 8, right**). For this dust scene, TROPOMI detects this layer height at around 1650m and the calculated ALH_{bsc} from the lidar profile is placed at 2845m. It is postulated that the center of the assumed layer height by the TROPOMI operational algorithm is lower to the actual layer location calculated as ALH_{bsc} height (difference =1200 m).

Figure 8. (Left) (a) backscatter coefficient profile at 1064 nm retrieved at the EARLINET station of Limassol and (b) resulting WCT profile on 10 January 2021, between 09:30–10:30 UTC. (Right) TROPOMI mean ALH (green dashed line) comparison to the retrieved lidar ALH_{bsc} (red dashed line).

As a general comment, Antikythera and Limassol were more privileged than other stations in observing a higher number of Saharan dust events since they are located closer to the African continent and generally

characterized by clearer atmospheric conditions. This is evident in the total number of Saharan dust events observed over these areas.

3.2 Analysis of the entire EARLINET collocations

Following the methodology summarized in **subsection 2.3**, we performed a validation analysis using lidar data from seven ground-based EARLINET sites located across the Mediterranean, spatio-temporally collected with data from TROPOMI instrument aboard Sentinel-5P satellite. The results of the comparison between the TROPOMI and EARLINET-derived aerosol heights for 25 identified collocated aerosol layers are shown in **Figure 9** which shows the scatterplot of TROPOMI ALH against EARLINET ALH_{b_{sc}} for all the common cases (N=25) used for the intercomparison. The mean maximum layer heights for all cases are, on average, 4.0 km (ranging between 2.15 and 9.98 km) and 2.8 km (ranging between 1.28 and 6.53 km) for EARLINET and TROPOMI, respectively. The accompanied related statistic metrics also presented in **Table 2** and **Table 3**. The regression approach revealed a good correlation between the two datasets, with **y-intercept=0.3**, **slope=0.63** and correlation coefficient **R=0.96** overall. Generally, it appears that aerosol layer altitudes retrieved from TROPOMI/S5P are systematically lower than ones obtained with ground-based lidars. The TROPOMI ALH values present a **negative absolute and relative bias on average -1.2±0.5 km and -28.5±12.0%** respectively compared to EARLINET retrievals. The EARLINET-TROPOMI differences, for all the available 25 cases of paired correlative observations, show a clear underestimation of the TROPOMI retrievals, in line with the validation against CALIOP/CALIPSO observations presented in Nanda et al., 2020.

Figure 9. Scatter plot of EARLINET retrieved ALH versus TROPOMI ALH data calculated from backscatter signals. The 1:1 line is plotted as a black line. The lidar measurements are taken from all the collocated TROPOMI pixels. The correlation coefficient is 0.96. The fit is $y=0.628x+0.298$. The uncertainties are the corresponding standard deviation of the mean.

Table 2. Statistics of the comparison between TROPOMI and EARLINET ALH datasets. The uncertainties are the corresponding standard deviation of the mean.

	N ^a	R ^b	Slope ^c	Y ^d	MB ^e (km)	RMSE ^f (km)	MRB ^g (%)
TROPOMI- EARLINET	25	0.96	0.628	0.298	-1.205	1.47	-28.56

^aNumber of collocations, ^bCorrelation coefficient, ^cSlope from linear regression fit, ^dY-intercept of linear regression fit, ^eMean bias, ^fRoot mean square error, ^gMean relative bias

Table 3. Layer height retrievals (average, min and max) of the EARLINET and TROPOMI ALH collocations.

	Min height (km)	Max height (km)	Average height (km)
TROPOMI	1.28	6.532	2.834 ± 1.342
EARLINET	2.15	9.982	4.064 ± 2.123

In the Framework of this project also the validation of GOME-2 against EARLINET database has been performed. The GOME-2 instrument, aboard the MetOp platforms can also detect and retrieve the optical properties of UV-absorbing aerosols like mineral dust and smoke by using the Absorbing Aerosol Index (AAI; Torres et al. 1998). Additionally, GOME-2 provides retrievals of Absorbing Aerosol Height (AAH) which is a new operational product for aerosol layer height detection, developed by KNMI within the EUMETASAT AC SAF. In Michailidis et al. (2021a), a large number of lidar datasets from 13 EARLINET stations was selected during the time period 2007-2019 in order to validate the GOME-2 AAH product. Finally, in total 172 collocated cases were found. The intercomparison results are very promising, showing that the GOME-2 AAH measurements provide a good estimation of the aerosol layer altitudes sensed by the EARLINET ground-based lidar instruments. On average, the mean absolute bias (GOME-2 minus lidar height) was found to be -0.18 ± 1.68 km, with a near-Gaussian distribution and minimum and maximum differences of $\sim \pm 5$ km. The overall agreement is quite satisfactory, with most lidar AAH values between 1 and 7 km. We have to note here that, in the case of the GOME-2 AAH retrievals, the algorithm (Wang et al. 2008) is able to determine the height of an absorbing aerosol layer not only in the absence of clouds but under certain conditions also in the presence of clouds. This is a basic difference between GOME-2 AAH and TROPOMI ALH retrievals. The software developed in the framework of this project for the systematic EARLINET versus GOME-2 and TROPOMI comparisons is continuously updated and modified taking into account new quality-assured data files.

4 Discussion

Overall, the analysis of TROPOMI ALH observations in the Mediterranean area shows high correlation with ground-based lidar observations, demonstrating the ability of the TROPOMI observations to properly capture the temporal variability of tropospheric aerosol plumes. This is a confirmation that satellite-based observations can provide additional information on the temporal and spatial variability of ALH in a continental scale. However, the requirement to use only sea pixels limits further the validation analysis in cases where extensive aerosol layers are detected over land. This condition significantly reduces the total number of available coincident cases. The current validation analysis needs to be extended to include more measurements, in order to enable detection of potential patterns, dependences and a more significant statistical analysis. In this work, we found that the TROPOMI altitudes are usually within the detected aerosol layer observed from lidar backscatter profiles. By defining a backscatter-weighted aerosol height from EARLINET aerosol backscatter profile products (ALH_{bsc}), the quantitative validation at pixels over the selected EARLINET stations illustrates that TROPOMI ALH is consistent with ALH_{bsc} , with a high correlation coefficient ($R=0.96$) and mean bias about -1.205 km. As a final point, it appears that aerosol layer altitudes retrieved from TROPOMI are systematically lower than altitudes from the lidar retrievals. Many factors play a role in this apparent disagreement between TROPOMI and the ground-based observations that can neither be attributed solely to the S5P data, nor to pure area-averaging differences. The strong possibility of remaining clouds in the TROPOMI field-of-view is one of the reasons why good spatial collocation with the lidar measurement was not achieved for every target pixel. Additionally, in many cases the spatial or temporal

distances to the target pixels can sometimes be quite large. The target requirement on accuracy and precision of retrieved aerosol layer height is 0.5 km or 50 hPa; the threshold requirement is 1 km or 100 hPa. Overall, our results related to the TROPOMI product appears to comply with the S5P mission requirements. These findings are also in good consistency with results obtained by other findings in the literature for TROPOMI ALH validation studies by Griffin et al. (2020) and Nanda et al. (2020).

5 Summary and Conclusions

The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height (ALH) product is a new and unique product providing global observations of aerosol height. TROPOMI aerosol layer heights can provide value to the modelling communities by improving air quality forecasting and providing improved air quality and radiative forcing studies. Aerosol plume heights from TROPOMI have the advantage of daily global coverage. In this study, the TROPOMI ALH is compared for the first time with the EARLINET database. The present report presents a cross-comparison analysis between TROPOMI and EARLINET data and provides a simple and well-developed methodology for comparing these different datasets. Lidar instruments retrieve the vertical backscatter coefficient, which is not directly comparable to the TROPOMI ALH product. Thus, the weighted-backscatter height (ALH_{bsc}) has to be calculated from the available backscatter profiles in the frame of this study. The Mediterranean basin is an ideal test environment for ALH features during extreme smoke or dust events. However, due to the product limitations over the land only sea pixels have been selected into the analysis study. Coincidences within a 150 km radius from the lidar station are used for direct observations, with a maximum of 3h time difference. All the input datasets considered in the study have been previously pre-processed at high resolution by using the EARLINET Single calculus chain (SCC). Overall, for 7 selected EARLINET stations across the Mediterranean, 25 coincident aerosol cases were found during the time period June 2018 - June 2021, checked and flagged for the comparison against satellite retrievals. The statistical results show the ability of the TROPOMI instrument to detect aerosol layers under cloud-free atmospheric conditions with significant aerosol load, such as dust and smoke plumes. Despite the different measuring concept that two instruments used for retrievals (passive & active), a good agreement ($R=0.96$) was found between TROPOMI retrievals and ground-based lidar measurements, demonstrating that TROPOMI has a quite promising potential for the characterization of the aerosol vertical distributions on a global scale. On average, the mean absolute bias (TROPOMI minus EARLINET data) was found to be -1.2 ± 0.86 km. Our findings are in a good agreement with other TROPOMI ALH validation studies (Griffin et al., 2020; Nanda et al., 2020).

This study highlights the importance of the synergistic use of active (ground-based lidars) and passive (satellite) observations and suggests a promising usage of TROPOMI ALH for understanding the details of the presence and transport of aerosol layers. The results of this study encourage the operational usage of the presented methodology approach in validation processes for satellite aerosol height products using lidar data from EARLINET. The increased availability of advanced and high quality-assured profiling data from EARLINET lidars will form a scientific background to improve performance of passive satellite sensors and lead to a better understanding of the role of the aerosol height on air-quality and the climate. For this reason, the further development of the validation methods is an on-going process in the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics (LAP-AUTH) aiming at extending the study domain from the regional to continental scale, considering the algorithm improvements (cloud screening and surface albedo fitting) provided by KNMI for Level-2 ALH retrievals.

References

- Apituley, A., M. Pedergnana, M. Sneep, J. P. Veefkind, D. Loyola, B. Sanders, M. de Graaf, Sentinel-5 precursor/TROPOMI Level 2 Product User Manual Aerosol Layer Height, CI-7570-PUM, issue: 2.0.0, date: 2021-06-24, S5P-KNMI-L2-0022-MA, <https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/documents/247904/2474726/Sentinel-5P-Level-2-Product-User-Manual-Aerosol-Layer-Height.pdf/cf2dcbbe-9354-41fa-9c69-61846d9980b7>, last access: 08.10.2021
- Graaf, M., J.F. de Haan and A.F.J. Sanders, TROPOMI ATBD of the Aerosol Layer Height, CI-7430-ATBD_Aerosol_Layer_Height, issue: 2.2.0, date: 2021-07-05, S5P-KNMI-L2-0006-RP, <https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/documents/247904/2476257/Sentinel-5P-TROPOMI-ATBD-Aerosol-Height>, last access: 08.10.2021.
- Amiridis, V., Balis, D. S., Giannakaki, E., Stohl, A., Kazadzis, S., Koukouli, M. E., and Zanis, P.: Optical characteristics of biomass burning aerosols over Southeastern Europe determined from UV-Raman lidar measurements, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 9, 2431–2440, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-9-2431-2009>, 2009.
- Amodeo, A., D'Amico, G., Giunta, A., Papagiannopoulos, N., Papayannis, A., Argyrouli, A., Mylonaki, M., Tsaknakis, G., Kokkalis, P., Soupiona, R., and Tzani, C.: ATHL16: the ATHens lidar intercomparison campaign, in: 28th international laser radar conference, Bucharest, Romania, 25–30 June 2017, 176, 09008, <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/201817609008>, 2018.
- Ansmann, A., Riebesell, M., Wandinger, U., Weitkamp, C., Voss, E., Lahmann, W., and Michaelis, W.: Combined Raman Elastic-Backscatter LIDAR for Vertical Profiling of Moisture, Aerosol Extinction, Backscatter, and LIDAR Ratio, *Appl. Phys. B*, 55, 18–28, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00348608>, 1992.
- Ansmann, A., Baars, H., Chudnovsky, A., Mattis, I., Veselovskii, I., Haarig, M., Seifert, P., Engelmann, R., and Wandinger, U.: Extreme levels of Canadian wildfire smoke in the stratosphere over central Europe on 21–22 August 2017, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 18, 11831–11845, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-18-11831-2018>, 2018.
- Baars, H., Ansmann, A., Engelmann, R., and Althausen, D.: Continuous monitoring of the boundary-layer top with lidar, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 8, 7281–7296, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-8-7281-2008>, 2008.
- Baars, H., Seifert, P., Engelmann, R., and Wandinger, U.: Target categorization of aerosol and clouds by continuous multiwavelength-polarization lidar measurements, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 10, 3175–3201, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-10-3175-2017>, 2017.
- Balis, D. S., Amiridis, V., Zerefos, C., Kazantzidis, A., Kazadzis, S., Bais, A. F., Meleti, C., Gerasopoulos, E., Papayannis, A., Matthias, V., Dier, H., and Andreae, M. O.: Study of the effect of different type of aerosols on UV-B radiation from measurements during EARLINET, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 4, 307–321, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-4-307-2004>, 2004.
- D'Amico, G., Amodeo, A., Baars, H., Biniotoglou, I., Freudenthaler, V., Mattis, I., Wandinger, U., and Pappalardo, G.: EARLINET Single Calculus Chain – overview on methodology and strategy, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 8, 4891–4916, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-8-4891-2015>, 2015.
- D'Amico, G., Amodeo, A., Mattis, I., Freudenthaler, V., and Pappalardo, G.: EARLINET Single Calculus Chain – technical – Part 1: Pre-processing of raw lidar data, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 491–507, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-491-2016>, 2016.
- de Graaf, M., Stammes, P., Torres, O., and Koelemeijer, R. B.: Absorbing Aerosol Index: Sensitivity analysis, application to GOME and comparison with TOMS, *J. Geophys. Res.-Atmos.* 110, 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JD005178>, 2005.
- Engelmann, R., Kanitz, T., Baars, H., Heese, B., Althausen, D., Skupin, A., Wandinger, U., Komppula, M., Stachlewska, I. S., Amiridis, V., Marinou, E., Mattis, I., Linné, H., and Ansmann, A.: The automated multiwavelength Raman polarization and water-vapor lidar PollyXT: the neXT generation, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 1767–1784, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-1767-2016>, 2016
- Hassinen, S., Balis, D., Bauer, H., Begoin, M., Delcloo, A., Eleftheratos, K., Gimeno Garcia, S., Granville, J., Grossi, M., Hao, N., Hedelt, P., Hendrick, F., Hess, M., Heue, K.-P., Hovila, J., Jönch-Sørensen, H., Kalakoski, N., Kauppi, A., Kiemle, S., Kins, L., Koukouli, M. E., Kujanpää, J., Lambert, J.-C., Lang, R., Lerot, C., Loyola, D., Pedergnana, M., Pinardi,

- G., Romahn, F., van Roozendaal, M., Lutz, R., De Smedt, I., Stammes, P., Steinbrecht, W., Tamminen, J., Theys, N., Tilstra, L. G., Tuinder, O. N. E., Valks, P., Zerefos, C., Zimmer, W., and Zyrichidou, I.: Overview of the O3M SAF GOME-2 operational atmospheric composition and UV radiation data products and data availability, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 383–407, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-383-2016>, 2016.
- Lelieveld J, Berresheim H, Borrmann S, Crutzen PJ, Dentener FJ, Fischer H, Feichter J, Flatau PJ, Heland J, Holzinger R, Korrmann R, Lawrence MG, Levin Z, Markowicz KM, Mihalopoulos N, Minikin A, Ramanathan V, De Reus M, Roelofs GJ, Scheeren HA, Sciare J, Schlager H, Schultz M, Siegmund P, Steil B, Stephanou EG, Stier P, Traub M, Warneke C, Williams J, Ziereis H. Global air pollution crossroads over the Mediterranean. *Science*. 2002 Oct 25;298(5594):794-9. doi: 10.1126/science.1075457. PMID: 12399583.
- Granados-Muñoz, M. J., Bravo-Aranda, J. A., Baumgardner, D., Guerrero-Rascado, J. L., Pérez-Ramírez, D., Navas-Guzmán, F., Veselovskii, I., Lyamani, H., Valenzuela, A., Olmo, F. J., Titos, G., Andrey, J., Chaikovskiy, A., Dubovik, O., Gil-Ojeda, M., and Alados-Arboledas, L.: A comparative study of aerosol microphysical properties retrieved from ground-based remote sensing and aircraft in situ measurements during a Saharan dust event, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 1113–1133, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-1113-2016>, 2016.
- Griffin, D., Sioris, C., Chen, J., Dickson, N., Kovachik, A., de Graaf, M., Nanda, S., Veefkind, P., Dammers, E., McLinden, C. A., Makar, P., and Akingunola, A.: The 2018 fire season in North America as seen by TROPOMI: aerosol layer height intercomparisons and evaluation of model-derived plume heights, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 13, 1427–1445, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-1427-2020>, 2020.
- Hassinen, S., Balis, D., Bauer, H., Begoin, M., Delcloo, A., Eleftheratos, K., Gimeno Garcia, S., Granville, J., Grossi, M., Hao, N., Hedelt, P., Hendrick, F., Hess, M., Heue, K.-P., Hovila, J., Jønch-Sørensen, H., Kalakoski, N., Kauppi, A., Kiemle, S., Kins, L., Koukoulis, M. E., Kujanpää, J., Lambert, J.-C., Lang, R., Lerot, C., Loyola, D., Pedernana, M., Pinardi, G., Romahn, F., van Roozendaal, M., Lutz, R., De Smedt, I., Stammes, P., Steinbrecht, W., Tamminen, J., Theys, N., Tilstra, L. G., Tuinder, O. N. E., Valks, P., Zerefos, C., Zimmer, W., and Zyrichidou, I.: Overview of the O3M SAF GOME-2 operational atmospheric composition and UV radiation data products and data availability, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 383–407, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-383-2016>, 2016.
- Holben, B. N., Eck, T. F., Slutsker, I., Tanre, D., Buis, J. P., Setzer, A., Vermote, E., Reagan, J. A., Kaufman, Y. J., Nakajima, T., Lavenu, F., Jankowiak, I., and Smirnov, A.: AERONET—a federated instrument network a data archive for aerosol characterization, *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 66, 1–16, 1998.
- Ingmann, P., Veihelmann, B., Langen, J., Lamarre, D., Stark, H., and Courrèges-Lacoste, G. B.: Requirements for the GMES Atmosphere Service and ESA's implementation concept: Sentinels-4/-5 and -5p, *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 120, 58–69, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.01.023>, 2012.
- IPCC, 2021: Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press. In Press.
- Kampouri, A., Amiridis, V., Solomos, S., Gialitaki, A., Marinou, E., Spyrou, C., Georgoulas, A.K., Akritidis, D., Papagiannopoulos, N., Mona, L., Scollo, S., Tsihla, M., Tsikoudi, I., Pytharoulis, I., Karacostas, T., and Zanis, P.: Investigation of Volcanic Emissions in the Mediterranean: “The Etna–Antikythera Connection”, *Atmosphere* 2021, 12(1), 40; <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12010040>, 2021.
- Kim, M.-H., Omar, A. H., Vaughan, M. A., Winker, D. M., Trepte, C. R., Hu, Y., Liu, Z., and Kim, S.-W.: Quantifying the low bias of CALIPSO's column aerosol optical depth due to undetected aerosol layers, *J. Geophys. Res.-Atmos.*, 122, 1098–1113, doi:10.1002/2016JD025797, 2017
- Klett, J. D.: Stable analytical inversion solution for processing lidar returns, *Appl. Optics*, 20, 211–220, 1981.
- Klett, J.: Lidar inversion with variable backscatter to extinction ratios, *Appl. Opt.*, 24, 1638–1643, 1985.
- Kokkalis P, Soupiona O, Papanikolaou C-A, Foskinis R, Mylonaki M, Solomos S, Vratolis S, Vasilatou V, Kralli E, Anagnou D, Papayannis A. Radiative Effect and Mixing Processes of a Long-Lasting Dust Event over Athens, Greece, during the COVID-19 Period. *Atmosphere*. 2021; 12(3):318. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12030318>, 2020
- Kooreman, M. L., Stammes, P., Trees, V., Sneep, M., Tilstra, L. G., de Graaf, M., Stein Zweers, D. C., Wang, P., Tuinder, O. N. E., and Veefkind, J. P.: Effects of clouds on the UV Absorbing Aerosol Index from TROPOMI, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 13, 6407–6426, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-6407-2020>, 2020.

- Mamouri, R. E., Ansmann, A., Nisantzi, A., Kokkalis, P., Schwarz, A., and Hadjimitsis, D.: Low Arabian dust extinction-to-backscatter ratio, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 40, 4762–4766, doi:10.1002/grl.50898, 2013.
- Mamouri, R.-E., Nisantzi, A., Engelman, R., Bühl, J., Seifert, P., Baars, H., Yin, Z., Hadjimitsis, D., and Ansmann, A.: The ERATOSTHENES CoE in the PollyNET: First observations of the PollyXT-CYP at Limassol, Cyprus, EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-16279, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-16279>, 2021.
- Michailidis, K., Koukoulis, M.-E., Siomos, N., Balis, D., Tuinder, O., Tilstra, L. G., Mona, L., Pappalardo, G., and Bortoli, D.: First validation of GOME-2/MetOp absorbing aerosol height using EARLINET lidar observations, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21, 3193–3213, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-3193-2021>, 2021a.
- Michailidis, K., Koukoulis, M.-E., Balis, D., et al., Validation of TROPOMI Aerosol layer height product using ground-based lidars: The role of the EARLINET database, in preparation, 2021b.
- Mona, L., Amodeo, A., Pandolfi, M., and Pappalardo, G.: Saharan dust intrusions in the Mediterranean area: three years of Raman lidar measurements, *J. Geophys. Res.-Atmos.*, 111, d16203, doi:10.1029/2005JD006569, 2006.
- Mona, L., Liu, Z., Müller, D., Omar, A., Papayannis, A., Pappalardo, G., Sugimoto, N., and Vaughan, M.: Lidar measurements for desert dust characterization: An overview, *Adv. Meteorol.*, 2012, 36 pp., <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/356265>, 2012.
- Nanda, S., de Graaf, M., Veefkind, J. P., ter Linden, M., Sneep, M., de Haan, J., and Levelt, P. F.: A neural network radiative transfer model approach applied to the Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument aerosol height algorithm, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 12, 6619–6634, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-6619-2019>, 2019.
- Nanda, S., de Graaf, M., Veefkind, J. P., Sneep, M., ter Linden, M., Sun, J., and Levelt, P. F.: A first comparison of TROPOMI aerosol layer height (ALH) to CALIOP data, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 13, 3043–3059, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-3043-2020>, 2020.
- Omar, A.: The CALIPSO Automated Aerosol Classification and Lidar Ratio Selection Algorithm, *J. Atmos. Ocean. Technol.*, 26, 1994–2014, 2009.
- Papayannis, A., Amiridis, V., Mona, L., Tsaknakis, G., Balis, D., Bösenberg, J., Chaikovski, A., De Tomasi, F., Grigorov, I., Mattis, I., Mitev, V., Müller, D., Nickovic, S., Perez, C., Pietruczuk, A., Pisani, G., Ravetta, F., Rizi, V., Sicard, M., Trickl, T., Wiegner, M., Gerding, M., Mamouri, R. E., D’Amico, G. and Pappalardo, G.: Systematic lidar observations of Saharan dust over Europe in the frame of EARLINET (2000–2002), *J. Geophys. Res.-Atmos. (AGU)*, 113(D10), D10204, 2008
- Pappalardo, G., Amodeo, A., Apituley, A., Comeron, A., Freudenthaler, V., Linné, H., Ansmann, A., Bösenberg, J., D’Amico, G., Mattis, I., Mona, L., Wandinger, U., Amiridis, V., Alados-Arboledas, L., Nicolae, D., and Wiegner, M.: EARLINET: towards an advanced sustainable European aerosol lidar network, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 7, 2389–2409, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-7-2389-2014>, 2014
- Omar, A.: The CALIPSO Automated Aerosol Classification and Li-dar Ratio Selection Algorithm, *J. Atmos. Ocean. Technol.*, 26, 1994–2014, 2009.
- Rolph, G., Stein, A., and Stunder, B.: Real-time Environmental Applications and Display system: READY, *Environ. Modell. Softw.*, 95, 210–228, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2017.06.025>, 2017.
- Sanders, A. F. J., de Haan, J. F., Sneep, M., Apituley, A., Stammes, P., Vieitez, M. O., Tilstra, L. G., Tuinder, O. N. E., Koning, C. E., and Veefkind, J. P.: Evaluation of the operational Aerosol Layer Height retrieval algorithm for Sentinel-5 Precursor: application to O2 A band observations from GOME-2A, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 8, 4947–4977, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-8-4947-2015>, 2015.
- Sentinel-5 precursor/TROPOMI Level 2 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document of the Aerosol Layer Heightsource: KNMI; ref: S5P-KNMI-L2-0006-RP; [url:https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/documents/247904/2476257/Sentinel-5P-TROPOMI-ATBD-Aerosol-Height](https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/documents/247904/2476257/Sentinel-5P-TROPOMI-ATBD-Aerosol-Height)
- Sentinel-5 precursor/TROPOMI Level 2 Product User Manual Aerosol Layer Heightsource: KNMI; ref: S5P-KNMI-L2-0026-MA; [url: https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/2474726/Sentinel-5P-Level-2-Product-User-Manual-Aerosol-Layer-Height](https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/2474726/Sentinel-5P-Level-2-Product-User-Manual-Aerosol-Layer-Height)
- Siomos, N., Balis, D. S., Voudouri, K. A., Giannakaki, E., Filioglou, M., Amiridis, V., Papayannis, A., and Fragkos, K.: Are EARLINET and AERONET climatologies consistent? The case of Thessaloniki, Greece, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 18, 11885–11903, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-18-11885-2018>, 2018.

- Stein Zweers, D. C.: TROPOMI ATBD of the UV aerosol index document number – S5P-KNMI-L2-0008-RP, KNMI, de Bilt, the Netherlands, CI-7430-ATBD_UVAI, p. 30, available at: <http://www.tropomi.eu/documents/atbd> (last access: 1 July 2021), 2018.
- Stein, A. F., Draxler, R. R., Rolph, G. D., Stunder, B. J. B., Cohen, M. D., and Ngan, F.: NOAA's hysplit atmospheric transport and dispersion modeling system, *B. Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, 96, 2059–2077, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00110.1>, 2015
- Torres, O., Bhartia, P. K., Herman, J. R., Ahmad, Z., and Gleason, J.: Derivation of aerosol properties from satellite measurements of backscattered ultraviolet radiation: Theoretical basis, *J. Geophys. Res.-Atmos.*, 103, 17099–17110, <https://doi.org/10.1029/98JD00900>, 1998.
- Wandinger, U., Freudenthaler, V., Baars, H., Amodeo, A., Engelmann, R., Mattis, I., Groß, S., Pappalardo, G., Giunta, A., D'Amico, G., Chaikovskiy, A., Osipenko, F., Slesar, A., Nicolae, D., Belegante, L., Talianu, C., Serikov, I., Linné, H., Jansen, F., Apituley, A., Wilson, K. M., de Graaf, M., Trickl, T., Giehl, H., Adam, M., Comerón, A., Muñoz-Porcar, C., Rocadenbosch, F., Sicard, M., Tomás, S., Lange, D., Kumar, D., Pujadas, M., Molero, F., Fernández, A. J., Alados-Arboledas, L., Bravo-Aranda, J. A., Navas-Guzmán, F., Guerrero-Rascado, J. L., Granados-Muñoz, M. J., Preißler, J., Wagner, F., Gausa, M., Grigorov, I., Stoyanov, D., Iarlori, M., Rizi, V., Spinelli, N., Boselli, A., Wang, X., Lo Feudo, T., Perrone, M. R., De Tomasi, F., and Burlizzi, P.: EARLINET instrument intercomparison campaigns: overview on strategy and results, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9, 1001–1023, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-1001-2016>, 2016
- Winker, D. M., Vaughan, M. A., Omar, A., Hu, Y., Powell, K. A., Liu, Z., Hunt, W. H., and Young, S. A.: Overview of the CALIPSO mission and CALIOP data processing algorithms, *J. Atmos. Ocean. Technol.*, 26, 2310–2323, <https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JTECHA1281.1>, 2009.

Data availability. EARLINET data used in this study are available from the authors and upon registration from the EARLINET web page at <https://data.earlinet.org/earlinet/login.zul> (Pappalardo et al., 2014). The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height (ALH) L2 data is the Reprocessed (RPRO, from June 2018 to April 2019) and Offline (OFFL, May 2019 to June 2021), version 01.03.02-01.04.00 dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5270/S5P-j7aj4gr>). The datafiles are publicly available via the Copernicus Open Data Access Hub (<https://s5phub.copernicus.eu/>, last access: 5 October 2021). Polly lidar observations (level 0 data, measured signals) are in the PollyNET database ([Pollynet, 2021](https://pollynet.org/)) with quicklooks at <http://polly.tropos.de>.

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Appendix A

A1. EARLINET Aerosol layering -Wavelet covariance transform (WCT)

This section aims at illustrating how the Wavelet covariance Transform method can be used on LIDAR backscatter profiles for layer detection. We use the wavelet covariance transform following the scheme proposed by Michailidis et al. (2021a). Details on the comparison approach are described in Michailidis et al. (2021a) for the validation of GOME-2 AAH data using EARLINET data. The aerosol geometrical properties carry information about the structure of lidar profiles, such as the boundary layer height and the features of the lofted aerosol layers, and can be obtained from any lidar profile. In this study, a full lidar dataset from 7 EARLINET stations has been used for the calculations. Some lidar optical products, however, are more reliable to use than others. For example, the longer wavelengths typically magnify the differences in the vertical distribution of the aerosol load, resulting in layers that are easier to identify. Furthermore, the Raman inversion always results in profiles that are less structured for the extinction coefficients than the backscatter coefficients. This is the reason why we prioritize them so as to produce geometrical properties (Baars et al., 2008; Siomos et al., 2017). The product with the highest potential to magnify the aerosol layer structure available is selected for each measurement. A critical parameter for the accurate WCT application is the selection of an appropriate value for the window (dilation), so as to distinguish cloud layers from aerosol layers. In our case, a dilation of 0.5 km is used for the selected backscatter profiles according to Baars et al. (2008). Then, the algorithm scans the profile, searching for pairs of boundaries (base-top). The PBL value is the first top layer (the first aerosol layer), with the ground being its basis. Details about the WCT method can be found in Siomos et al. (2018) and Michailidis et al. (2021a).

An example of a lidar backscatter profile with resulting WCT profile from the Antikythera (PANGEA-NOA) lidar station 27 May 2019 is given in **Figure A 1**. This figure shows the ability of the lidar to detect multiple layers. The horizontal dashed blue and red lines represent the detected aerosol layer base and top applying the WCT methodology, and two aerosol layers are detected, according to the followed methodology.

Figure A 1. Antikythera PollyXT lidar (PANGEA- NOA): (Left) lidar backscatter profile at 1064 nm and (Right) resulting WCT profile on 27 May 2019 (Details as figure) The horizontal dashed red and blue lines represent the detected aerosol layer top and base applying the WCT methodology. The label “S–G” indicates that a Savitzky–Golay filter was used to signal smoothing. The yellow horizontal line represents the center of mass for each detected layer.

A2. List of collocated cases between EARLINET & TROPOMI

In the following we provide, in **Table A 1**, the list of the 25 collocated cases found for the period studied while the associated comparative profiles are provided in **Figure A 2**, **Figure A 3** and **Figure A 4**.

Table A 1. List of collocated EARLINET – TROPOMI cases including the station name, date of observation and the reported ALH by TROPOMI and EARLINET.

Station Name	EARLINET code	Date	TROPOMI ALH (m)	EARLINET ALH _{bsc} (m)
Antikythera	AKY	23-05-2019	2980.1	4070
Antikythera	AKY	27-05-2019	3159	3500
Antikythera	AKY	28-05-2019	2849.6	3000
Antikythera	AKY	14-05-2020	2991	3820.2
Antikythera	AKY	15-05-2020	2164	3340
Antikythera	AKY	26-10-2020	5421.2	9050.1
Antikythera	AKY	27-10-2020	4700	7100
Antikythera	AKY	22-06-2021	2549.4	3010.3
Antikythera	AKY	09-01-2021	1570.2	2151.2
Athens	ATZ	15-05-2020	2445	3057
Limassol	CYC	27-03-2020	1800	2300
Limassol	CYC	10-01-2021	1651	2845.3
Limassol	CYC	10-03-2021	2457.3	3500
Limassol	CYC	15-03-2021	1709.8	2600
Limassol	CYC	22-03-2021	1285	2500
Limassol	CYC	06-04-2021	2675	3900
Potenza	POT	26-10-2020	5553.4	8050
Lecce	SAL	13-05-2020	2901	3850
Lecce	SAL	14-05-2020	3143.6	3250
Granada	GRA	11-07-2018	2164.2	3125
Granada	GRA	15-07-2018	2707	4500
Granada	GRA	01-08-2018	2100	3605.2
Évora	EVO	18-03-2020	1800.2	2450
Évora	EVO	19-03-2020	1594	3080.2
Évora	EVO	24-10-2020	6503	9300.3

Figure A 2. Backscatter vertical profiles at 532 and 1064nm retrieved by Antikythera (AKY) lidar station used in the validation study. The horizontal green and red dashed lines represent the TROPOMI ALH and ALH_{bsc} altitude.

National Technical University of Athens, Physics Department - NTUA
Location: [23.78°E / 37.96°N], Athens, Greece
Date: 2020-05-15T15:50:45Z-2020-05-15T16:50:47Z

Cyprus University of Technology (CUT), Limassol - CUT
Location: [33.04°E / 34.67°N], Limassol, Cyprus
Date: 2020-03-27T10:37:48Z-2020-03-27T12:36:18Z

Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research, Leipzig - TROPOS
Location: [33.04°E / 34.68°N], Limassol CyCare, Germany
Date: 2021-01-10T09:31:00Z-2021-01-10T10:31:00Z

Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research, Leipzig - TROPOS
Location: [33.04°E / 34.68°N], Limassol CyCare, Germany
Date: 2021-03-15T12:30:00Z-2021-03-15T13:27:00Z

Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research, Leipzig - TROPOS
Location: [33.04°E / 34.68°N], Limassol CyCare, Germany
Date: 2021-03-22T08:30:01Z-2021-03-22T09:21:31Z

Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research, Leipzig - TROPOS
Location: [33.04°E / 34.68°N], Limassol CyCare, Germany
Date: 2021-04-06T09:30:03Z-2021-04-06T10:30:03Z

Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research, Leipzig - TROPOS
Location: [33.04°E / 34.68°N], Limassol CyCare, Germany
Date: 2021-03-10T08:30:00Z-2021-03-10T09:21:30Z

University of Salento, Physics Department, Lecce
Location: [18.1°E / 40.33°N], Lecce, Italy
Date: 2020-05-13T10:47:00Z-2020-05-13T11:46:30Z

National Observatory of Athens - NOA
Location: [23.31°E / 35.86°N], Antikythera, Greece
Date: 2020-05-14T11:00:27Z-2020-05-14T12:31:27Z

Figure A 3. Backscatter vertical profiles at 532 and 1064nm retrieved by Athens (ATZ), Limassol (LIM, CYC) and Lecce (SAL) lidar stations used in the validation study. The horizontal green and red dashed lines represent the TROPOMI ALH and ALH_{bsc} altitude.

Figure A 4. Backscatter vertical profiles at 532 and 1064nm retrieved by Évora (EVO) and Granada (GRA) lidar stations used in the validation study. The horizontal green and red dashed lines represent the TROPOMI ALH and ALH_{bsc} altitude.

A3. Validation methodology Flowchart

Figure A 5. Schematic flow chart showing the main steps of the methodology applied in this study to obtain the collocation datasets from the EARLINET and TROPOMI/S5P measurements.